

HOMOGENEITY OF NANOPARTICLE LAYERS AS DEPOSITED BY GAS PHASE CONDENSATION (GPC) AND PE-CVD PROCESSES

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Abstract:

We report on the bottom-up, in vacuum synthesis of nanoparticle layers on static substrates with areas of up to 150 x 200 mm by vapor-phase condensation combined with an additional PE-CVD source for the deposition of organic (plasma polymer) or inorganic dielectric matrix materials. Nanoparticles embedded in a thin film matrix have a wide range of potential applications, from antiviral and antibacterial surfaces, over water treatment, (photo-)catalysis, sensing, and structured surfaces for condensation and heat transfer. Ag, Ti, and Pt nanoparticles are obtained from inert gas phase condensation (GPC) of sputtered atomic vapor, stemming from an inert Gas Flow Sputtering (GFS) source. This method is suitable for the production of virtually all existing metals. Here, we present the stability and the homogeneity of the resulting nanoparticle layers (Ag and Pt NPs). To further inspect the homogeneity of the nanoparticle deposition process, Ag NP / SiO_x multilayer nanocomposite layers (embedded nanoparticles in a dielectric matrix) are examined by X-ray diffraction. The synthesis/structure/morphology relations are presented for both the initial random deposition (Ag) as well as the highly porous structure (Ti) obtained during later stages of deposition. Nanoparticle size and structures are investigated and the control of nanoparticles size distribution by both pressure in the aggregation zone and discharge power is reported.

Keywords

nanoparticles, sputtering, gas phase aggregation, nanocomposite, nanotechnology, XRD, TEM, SEM

Introduction:

Nanoparticles (NPs) have a wide variety of applications both in research and industry. NPs can be generated by various processes such as biological methods, wet chemistry, power-ball milling, flame pyrolysis, laser pyrolysis, spark aerosol, pulsed laser ablation, gas phase aggregation, or lithography. The respective share of these methods for the production of iron oxide NPs is presented in [1]. Biological and wet chemistry methods (92% of papers) and power-ball milling (1%) can be relatively inexpensive and allow the production of NPs in very large quantities but are limited by the unavoidable presence of a large amounts of impurities, such as surfactant emulsifiers, catalysts, or residues from balls and containers. Precursor-based physical methods (2.5%) such as flame, and laser pyrolysis can also produce NPs in relatively large quantities, but these NP contain (in a lesser amount) impurities coming from precursor and reaction products. Lithography (0.5%) allows the deposition of complex shapes and precise positioning, but is limited to small deposition area, and is relatively slow and expensive. Plasma-based physical methods (4%), such as spark aerosol, laser ablation and gas-phase aggregation, produce NPs with the lowest amounts of impurities. Among them, gas-phase aggregation is an *in vacuo*, purely physical process achieving high purity nanoparticles, potentially in a relatively large quantity. Gas phase aggregation has been previously demonstrated for synthesis of metal, metal oxides, and plasma polymers NPs, alone [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7] or in combination in metal-polymer nanocomposites [8, 9, 10], and resulted in new findings in fundamental aspects such as NP growth process [11, 12,13, 14, 15], NP sizes, velocity, and charge distributions [16, 17, 18, 19, 20].

In this work, we present a nanomaterial vacuum deposition process combining a nanoparticle (NPs) source and a matrix material thin film source. Nanoparticles are generated by Gas Flow Sputtering (GFS), a purely physical synthesis process allowing for NPs with the highest purity. A rotating sample holder carries the sample under a Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition (PE-CVD) source for the direct encapsulation of the NPs in a matrix, thus allowing a safe-by-design *in vacuo* fixation of NPs in multilayer nanocomposites. This process allows the deposition of pure nanoparticles layers, pure matrix material layers, nanocomposite coatings, and multilayer structures made of alternating nanocomposite and matrix material coatings. The rotating sample holder permits continuous multilayer depositions on up to 200 x 1300 mm on flexible substrates. Both substrate size and achieved total deposition rates (in the order of 200 nm/min) make this process suitable for upscaling and industrial application. It has been used for the deposition of nanocomposite coatings, as advanced TiO₂ photocatalytic thin films [21], conductive polymer composites for sensors [22], plasmonic coatings [23], and structured surfaces for condensation, heat transfer [24], and filtration [25].

We report here on Ag, Ti, and Pt nanoparticles: The stability and the homogeneity of the resulting nanoparticle layers is first presented in the case of Ag and Pt NPs; then, X-ray diffraction results are presented for Ag NP (in SiO_x matrix layer); finally, microscopy of Ag and Ti NP deposition are presented and the effects of both pressure in the aggregation zone and discharge power on nanoparticles size distribution are discussed.

Experimental:

The deposition of nanocomposite coatings is achieved using an experimental system (Figure 1) composed of a gas phase condensation (GPC) unit for the generation of nanoparticles, a PE-CVD unit for the deposition of matrix material, and a rotating sample holder to transport the sample between both sources. Nanoparticles (e.g. Ti, Ag, ITO) are synthesized by the inert gas phase condensation of the atomic vapor sputtered from the gas flow sputtering source and carried with the gas flow onto the substrate holder in

the main chamber. A low-pressure PE-CVD source allows the deposition of organic (Plasma Polymer) or inorganic dielectric matrix coatings.

Figure 1: Schematic of the nanocomposite deposition system according to [26].

The presented setup allows maximum flexibility regarding the choice of materials for nanocomposite fabrication. It can incorporate inorganic (metals, semiconductors, oxides, inorganic composites) NPs into matrix materials, such as polymers, oxides, and other inorganic composites. It allows the deposition of pure NP layers, pure matrix material layers, nanocomposite coatings, and multilayer structures made of alternating nanocomposite and matrix material coatings.

A base vacuum of $7.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ Pa is achieved with two turbomolecular pumps (Balzers TCP 1600 L/s and Varian V 250 L/s for deposition and aggregation volumes, respectively). During deposition process, the NP carrier gas flow in main vessel (deposition volume) is evacuated by Edwards EH2600 Mechanical Booster Pump and E2M275 Rotary Vacuum Pump. The pumping power is controlled in real time by exhaust throttle valve, pressure controller and pressure sensor (MKS 653B, 651C and Typ 122) in order to achieve constant deposition and aggregation pressures. Meanwhile the PE-CVD reactor is isolated from the main deposition volume and separately pumped by a roots vacuum pumping station (Pfeiffer WOT 400 D-4) fitted with gas ballast and PTFE inert lubricant. This allows the removal of potentially corrosive and explosive reaction products.

Nanoparticle source: Hollow cathode Gas flow sputtering

The gas flow sputter source (GFS) is a specially designed hollow-cathode, developed by the Fraunhofer Institute for Surface Engineering and Thin Films (IST, Braunschweig) for high-rate thin films and nanoparticle deposition [27, 28]. Hollow cathode sources are able to achieve high plasma density (N_e , in our case up to $6 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) as a result of the pendulum effect where oscillating electrons transfer their kinetic energy and ionize Ar atoms [29]. The pendulum effect is observed at sufficiently low pressure and intensifies with increasing supply of neutral Ar atoms. The glow discharges of the two targets superimpose to form a hollow cathode discharge. In this hollow cathode discharge, a stream of inert gas carries the sputtered atoms out of the plasma discharge zone. The vapor exits the source with carrier flow and the sputtered atoms thermalize in the inert gas atmosphere. The following aggregation zone is maintained at a controlled pressure 10 to 100 Pa to foster the formation of clusters and nanoparticles. The aggregation zone is separated from the deposition chamber by an adjustable orifice, allowing to control separately both pressures in the aggregation and in the deposition zones. Pressure is kept between 1 and 10 Pa in the

deposition zone. Experimentally, average electron temperature (T_e) is maintained in the range 2 ± 0.3 eV while plasma density values reach $2 \cdot 10^{11}$ to $5 \cdot 10^{12}$ cm^{-3} , for 2000 and 3000 sccm, respectively. Average electron temperature slowly declines with higher aggregation pressure (10% loss for 50 to 100 Pa), while plasma density sharply falls, losing 60% to 90% in the same pressure range. Increased optical emission confirming the hollow cathode effect is observed above 2000 sccm and below 55 Pa. Higher atom density achieved by this source is the cause of the high deposition rates reported in this work. Plasma conditions in the source are detailed in [30]

Matrix source: PE-CVD reactor

The PE-CVD unit consists of a 60 MHz Radio-Frequency (RF) capacitive coupled discharge, presented in greater details in [30], and of an evaporator providing chemical precursors with vapor pressures in the range of 100 to 10 000 Pa. Hexamethyldisiloxane (HMDSO, Sigma Aldrich 99%) was used without further purification and heated at 40°C for vaporizing. Gaseous monomer precursor, reactive (O_2 , N_2) and inert (Ar) gases are regulated individually by four mass flow controllers (MKS). The high frequency plasma achieves a higher degree of ionization (in the range of 10^{11} cm^{-3}) as compared to standard 13.56 MHz plasma, while average electron temperature reaches 5 to 10 eV. The PE-CVD unit allows deposition rates up to 200 nm/min over 340 x 100 mm deposition area and is suitable for the deposition of functional plasma polymers on large area and has been described in further details in [31, 32, 33]. This process allows maximum flexibility regarding the choice of materials, with matrix materials such as polymers, oxides, and all common PE-CVD thin films. Here, organic-inorganic (SiO_xC_y to SiO_2) thin films were obtained by changing O_2 partial pressure in plasma, with deposition rates in the order of 200 nm/min.

Diagnostics and analytics

The aggregation chamber is equipped with a compact optical emission spectrometer (Ocean Optics USB4000) enabling the analysis of the gas flow sputtering discharge. The optical signal is coupled out via a silver mirror, a quartz window, through low-OH multimode optical fiber, and optical fiber collimator. Calibration is done with a known source spectrum (Ocean Optics DH2000 Halogen + Deuterium lamp). Plotting $\ln(I_{ki} \cdot \lambda_{ki} / A_{ki} \cdot g_k)$ as a function of the highest level Energy E_k (Boltzmann's plot) allows an estimation of the electron temperature in the discharge. Electron density N_e is estimated by actinometry from the intensity ratio of the emission lines of excited 5p and 3p states of the argon carrier gas.

In order to characterize nanoparticle sizes, depositions were carried out on Si wafers and imaged with scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi SU8000). The NPs size distributions were then calculated from the SEM micrographs (100.000x magnification and a sampled area of 1.13 μm^2) with an image analysis software (Photoshop). Further analysis of individual nanoparticles was carried out by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, 200 kV Philips CM200 equipped with super twin objective lens and tungsten filament, point resolution $\Delta r = 0.25$ nm).

In order to characterize the domain sizes, multilayer (nanoparticle-matrix) nanocomposite layers were deposited on glass, and diffraction patterns were collected on a X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Bruker Axs D8 Discover) using the copper K- α emission at 8.04 keV. Crystalline domains size was estimated from the Scherrer equation (Eq. 1) linking XRD line broadening at full width half maximum intensity (FWHM) with the mean size of the ordered (crystalline) domains within the sample [34]:

$$D = 0.94 \lambda / \beta \cos(\theta) \quad (1)$$

with D the average crystallite domain size, λ the X-ray wavelength, β the full width at half maximum (FWHM), and θ the diffraction angle.

Results & Discussion:

In this section, we first present the characterization of the deposition source by Optical emission spectrometry (OES, Ag NPs), and in terms of deposition area (Ag & Pt NPs). NPs are then characterized by XRD (Ag NPs in SiO_x matrix layer), TEM (Ag NPs). Finally, results for particle size distribution by SEM (Ag NPs) and for cross-section SEM (Ti NPs) are presented.

NP Source stability (Ag)

The design of applicable plasma processes requires a stability and repeatability of the process. For this reason, it is important to evaluate the stability of the sputtering process. Figure 2 shows the OES measurements that were carried out for various carrier gas flow values ((a) 600 sccm, 27 Pa; (b) 900 sccm, 38 Pa; (c) 1200 sccm, 48 Pa; 1500 sccm, 58 Pa) during the synthesis of silver NPs. Silver (green) and argon (purple) emissions are displayed on the right scale, total optical emission (black) on the left scale. The data show relatively stable optical total emissions, Ag and Ar peaks with total variations in the order of 5%.

Average emission of silver is enhanced with increasing pressure and ion bombardment, while argon emissions reach maximum at 38 Pa and decrease at higher pressures, as collision rate and thermalization possibly reduce the number of spontaneous photon emission. Observed slopes of the emission curves may be linked to the desorption of heteroatoms such as oxygen adsorbed superficially on the target. Such phenomena can have significant influence on the aggregation process and nanoparticles sizes [35] but do not directly affect the stability of the discharge.

Figure 2: Optical emission stability as collected in various conditions: 600 sccm $P_{aggr.}$ 27 Pa $P_{dep.}$ 5.1 Pa (a), 900 sccm $P_{aggr.}$ 38 Pa $P_{dep.}$ 6.8 Pa (b), 1200 sccm $P_{aggr.}$ 48 Pa $P_{dep.}$ 8.3 Pa (c), 1500 sccm $P_{aggr.}$ 58 Pa $P_{dep.}$ 9.9 Pa (d). Silver (green) and argon (purple) emissions are displayed on the right scale, total optical emission (black) on the left scale.

NP Source homogeneity (Ag, Pt)

In order to display the total area of the NP deposition zone, we deposited nanoparticles on chlorine-free, 80 g/m² white A4 paper sheets. Paper is attached on the substrate holder. After NP deposition, the NP-coated papers are sealed in clear 80µm polypropylene sheath and scanned (photographs in Figure 3). The depth of the coated area is related to the NP deposition rate, darker areas correspond to higher fill-factor and deposition rates. The 2 blue lines show the limits of the flat deposition area.

As presented in the case of silver NPs in Figure 3(a-d), slit orifice width and gas flows have been varied in order to modify carrier gas flow at a constant aggregation pressure. For a thinner opening, a lower carrier gas flow is needed which results in low deposition rate. For a wider opening, the maximal gas flow is soon reached, and lower aggregation pressure also results in low deposition rate. An experimental optimum is found around 2 to 3 mm width.

As presented in the case of platinum NPs in Figure 4(a-d), pressure and power were varied using a constant slit orifice width between the aggregation and the deposition volumes. In that case, the deposition area is wide and near optimal for all conditions. The deposition is darker (higher deposition rate) at 1 kW 57 Pa as at 3 kW 57 Pa but is lighter (lower deposition rate) at 1 kW 80 Pa as at 3 kW 88 Pa increasing, thus the deposition rate does not evolve proportionally with power, but optimal power-and-pressure conditions have to be determined for highest deposition rates.

Meanwhile, a deformation of the deposition zone (asymmetric vertically, in hourglass shape) is noticeable everywhere, increasingly at higher jet velocity (thinner slit width, higher gas flow) and higher pressure (less diffusion). The shape is explained by the impinging plane jet spreading out around the substrate surface while flowing downwards toward the pumps, thus broadening at the bottom.

Thus, a deposition area of up to 150 x 200 mm can be covered with NPs, however with some inhomogeneity. In the meantime, nanoparticle deposition with a homogeneity of $\pm 5\%$ were demonstrated on an area of up to 65 x 115 mm (represented as a red dotted line in Figure 4a).

Figure 3: Photographs of deposition area for Ag NPs at constant aggregation pressure: (a) 1 mm 500 sccm 3.5 kW (b) 2mm 1400 sccm 1.5 kW (c) 3 mm 1500 sccm 1.5 kW (d) 3 mm 2500 sccm 2.5 kW. Deposition time: 6 min.

Figure 4: Deposition area for Pt NPs with 2 mm slit width: (a) 1 kW 57 Pa (b) 3 kW 57 Pa (c) 1 kW 80 Pa (d) 3 kW 81 Pa. Deposition time: 5 min.

NP size homogeneity (Ag NP / SiO_x)

It is well established that nanoparticles produced by gas phase aggregation are distributed in both size, velocity, and charge [36, 37, 38]. Here, we investigate the homogeneity of the deposited NPs: 5 nanoparticle and 5 PE-CVD SiO_x layers were alternatively deposited on glass to form Ag NP / SiO_x multilayer nanocomposite coatings. Each nanoparticle layer was obtained at 68 Pa with 1200 sccm Ar flow, 3 kW sputter power, 1 min deposition time, each PE-CVD SiO_x layer was deposited at 500 W, and 1 min deposition time. We used XRD to study the crystalline structure of the NP in the amorphous matrix, on amorphous (glass) substrates. The nanoparticles are expected to be mono-crystalline, therefore crystal size can provide a good estimation of the maximal NP size. Figure 5 presents the XRD Spectra taken at 4 different points placed at 0, 15, 20 and 25 mm from the sample center, represented in green, black, red, and blue, respectively (corresponding points shown in Figure 4e).

Four distinct diffraction peaks were observed at 2θ angles 38.06° , 44.37° , 64.73° and 77.82° . They were assigned to (1 1 1), (2 0 0), (2 2 0) and (3 1 1) planes respectively, indicating the silver nanoparticles are crystalline in nature and have a face-centered cubic (fcc) structure.

The Scherrer method was carried out on several diffraction peaks without obtaining significant deviation in the extrapolated values for NP size. As presented in Table 1, no evidence of any significant NP domain size variation between impingement region ($x = 0$) and neighboring region could be identified, confirming the NP deposition is homogeneous in both deposition rate and in nanoparticle size at least 25 mm on each side of the deposition center.

Figure 5: XRD Spectrum of an Ag NP/ SiO_x coating sample. Scherrer size estimates given for each angle.

Table 1: NP Domain size estimated by the Scherrer method for measurement points at various distances (x) from the sample center.

x (mm)	Domain size (nm)
0	39 ±10
-15	48 ±7
-20	39 ±8
-25	34 ±14

As a fcc metal, silver exhibits minimal surface energy in (1 1 1) planes (620 ergs/cm²), surface energy increasing with increasing angle with following (h k l) planes from 752.33, 833.48, and 835.86 ergs/cm² for (2 0 0), (2 2 0) and (3 1 1) planes, respectively [39]. As (1 1 1) texture is expected to be favored in thin films, platelets and/or flat-shaped Ag particles [40], further crystallographic planes are expected to appear in diffraction pattern for round NP, for example (2 0 0) has the smallest angle difference to (1 1 1) plane. Thus, XRD spectrum presented in Figure 5 suggests the particles are predominantly spherical/polyhedral in shape and arranged in a random order. Meanwhile, for a constant atomic deposition rate, and if atoms are prevented to move to energy-favorable sites, (2 0 0) planes, although not as compact as (1 1 1) planes, have been shown to grow faster along the growth direction due to their lower atomic density [41]. The (2 0 0) planes also appear on dark-field TEM pictures of evaporated silver NPs in the classical work of Marks [42] (fig.3, p.83).

Nanoparticles characterization and nanoparticle sizes (Ag, Ti)

Figure 6: TEM images of Ag NPs ($P = 3$ kW, $f_{Ar} = 5000$ sccm, $P_{agg} = 70$ Pa). Lattice parameter $a = 237$ pm [30]. In inset, Mark's decahedron structures [42].

The deposited Ag Nanoparticles in the PE-CVD matrix were further analyzed by TEM (Figure 6). We measured the lattice parameter $a = 237$ pm in the cF-orientation 110, corresponding to 99.999% pure silver [43]. The particle presents a known 5- faceted (Mark's decahedron) structure, corresponding to minimal surface energy, as detailed in [42, 44].

Figure 7 presents the evolution of average nanoparticle size as characterized by manual analysis on SEM pictures (not shown). Average nanoparticle size measured by this method range from 3 to 20 nm for 3 kW power. For 3 kW, 1200 sccm Ar, the average expected size for the NPs is 13 nm, while the domain size estimates obtained by the Scherrer formula on XRD spectra (Figure 5) are significantly higher (34 to 48 nm), although the NPs are synthesized under the same conditions. First, since the domain size is not smaller than expected NP sizes, we conclude that nanoparticles are monocrystalline, and not composed of multiple smaller crystallite units, confirming TEM observations discussed earlier. Also, hypotheses can be formulated to explain the observed discrepancy between SEM and XRD sizes: we suggest it may result from indistinguishable XRD response from nanoparticles aggregated into larger groups, coalescence of close neighbor nanoparticles under X-Ray illumination, from uncertainties of the XRD spectra acquisition resulting in large size variation due to the $1/\beta$ dependance in Scherrer equation (Eq. 1).

As it can be seen in Figure 7, NP size as a function of carrier gas flow first decreases and reaches a minimal value for a gas flow of 2000 sccm, then increases with higher gas flows, following a pattern similar to that of both electron temperature and plasma density: For low gas flows and pressures, medium T_e (~ 2 eV) and N_e ($\sim 2 \cdot 10^{12}$) values are achieved, and longer residence time results in increased aggregation and larger NP sizes. Higher gas flows and pressures result in shorter residence time and reduced aggregation, low T_e (< 1.8 eV) and much lower N_e ($5 \cdot 10^{11}$). For even higher gas flows and pressures, the hollow cathode effect results in higher T_e (~ 2.4 eV) and much higher N_e ($5 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), the high plasma density allows increased aggregation and higher NP sizes due to higher collision rate.

Figure 7: Size of Ag particles as a function of Ar carrier gas flow in the aggregation zone. (70 Pa, 3 kW)

Thus, both deposition rate (see Figure 3), plasma parameters, and NP sizes share a non-linear relation to power and pressure, and optimal power-and-pressure conditions must be determined experimentally. For instance, highest deposition rate is obtained at 60 Pa for 0.5 kW, 70 Pa for 1 kW, 85 Pa for 1.5 kW, and above 100 Pa for higher power, the deposition rate at 100 Pa then decreasing with increasing power between 2 and 3.5 kW. In the case presented in Figure 8, higher injected power results in lower particle sizes due to higher sputtering rate, while a higher pressure results in a wider size distribution and higher average sizes due to increased collision probability and growth dynamics of the nanoparticles [21, 23,30, 45].

Figure 8: Size of Ag particles at $P_{agg} = 67$ Pa as a function of electrical power $P = 1.5$ kW (a) and $P = 5$ kW (b). Size of Ag particles size at $P = 3$ kW with increasing pressure $P_{agg} = 40$ Pa (c) and $P_{agg} = 104$ Pa (d). Ar flow 2000 sccm in all cases [30]

NPs are initially deposited randomly and homogeneously on the substrate surface (see Figure 8). During later stages of deposition, NPs aggregate and form a highly porous structure with low adhesion (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Highly porous Ti NP aggregate, SEM cross-section, $P = 4 \text{ kW}$, $f_{Ar} = 1800 \text{ sccm}$, $P = 91.4 \text{ Pa}$

This phenomenon is avoided for the deposition of nanocomposite coatings: NPs and matrix multilayer coatings requires short NPs deposition time, and NPs fill factor well below percolation threshold, so that the matrix thin film adheres to both substrate and NPs.

Conclusion:

We present a novel nanomaterial deposition process with good source stability and large deposition area. Good homogeneity of the NP deposition was confirmed by X-ray diffraction of immobilized nanoparticles in an inorganic dielectric matrix. Individual NPs and NPs layers were investigated by TEM, SEM and cross-section SEM at various stages of deposition, allowing to analysis of individual NP crystallographic structure and purity (>99.999% in the case of silver), as well as both initial random deposition and highly porous structure obtained at later stages thereof. Finally, control of the NPs size distribution by aggregation pressure and discharge power was presented. Our results confirm the potential of this process to provide ultra-pure NPs. Our experimental setup allows the combination of high-purity NPs deposition with PE-CVD matrix thin film source for safe-by-design *in vacuo* inclusion of NPs into nano-composite layers for various potential applications in medical (antiviral / antibacterial surfaces) environmental and energy (water treatment, catalysis and fuel cells) optics and microelectronics (biosensor, plasmonic layers) fields.

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